

METHODS OF TEACHING STUDENTS TO TEXT PROBLEMS AND SOLVE THEM IN PRIMARY CLASS MATHEMATICS LESSONS

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Enter. Currently, in developed countries around the world, great attention is being paid to the education of young people, and state programs on these issues are also being adopted. In this regard, fundamental reforms are being carried out in the continuous education system of Uzbekistan, and issues of intellectual level, knowledge, outlook and competitiveness of the acquired knowledge of young people are being analyzed in them. After all, "our main goal is to build a new Uzbekistan. But we also understand that it cannot be built without young people. It is crucial to ensure the rights and interests of the growing youth, to educate them as selfless children of our country." Based on these goals, to develop the thinking, way of thinking and worldview of schoolchildren, mathematical thinking, speed of calculation, knowledge of the environment and the world, worldview, attitude to events, the way of thinking based on the formation of the conscious attitude of students activity development was defined as an important task.

The following goals are set for the acquired knowledge in this field:

- every theoretical knowledge given should be formed on the basis of the process that needs to be mastered by the student. In this case, the final results of the synthesis of assimilation and other multiplications should be reflected on the basis of acquired knowledge;
- the imparted knowledge should be perfect and it should be possible to acquire it sufficiently and to be able to apply this knowledge in practice. This ultimately allows training of personnel that meets the requirements of the international labor and services market.
- on the basis of the above: it is determined by the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in situations of frequent changes and to make the right decisions on time;
- acquired knowledge must be at a sufficient level. For this, choosing the most convenient and suitable for the studied topic among the various approaches by developing methods for solving issues related to the studied topic;

➤ acquired knowledge is required to be clear and able to generalize concepts related to the subject under consideration. In this case, the skill of clarifying the specific manifestation of generalized knowledge, deepening the acquired knowledge on the basis of generalization, transition from specific to general (induction) is achieved.

It is appropriate for the teacher to take into account the following when forming the real knowledge of the results of solving textual problems for students in elementary mathematics classes:

✚ achieving knowledge acquisition by students, that is, being able to use it in future practical activities;

✚ that the knowledge formed by students corresponds to their age and level of education (what class they are studying in);

✚ that the student can justify every acquired new knowledge with evidence.

The systematic organization of solving textual problems for students in primary grade mathematics lessons forms their skills of mastering the studied educational materials.

The result of solving text problems for students in elementary mathematics lessons is the high level of information they have mastered. It is manifested in the process of setting and solving information problems and tasks.

the analysis of the literature devoted to the improvement of the teaching of mathematics in primary grades in psychological-pedagogical research is one of the ways to increase the effectiveness of teaching mathematics in primary grades, to change the content of education by enriching information, to change the didactic elements. (BPYerdniyev, PMYerdniyev), separating the main idea of each subject (IDZverev, VNMaksimova, R.A. Mavlonova, A.Abduqadirov, A.M. Markushevish) increasing the role of theoretical knowledge (VVDavidov, A.K .Markova, J.Ikromov, A.M.Pishkalo, L.Sh.Levenberg, NUBikbaeva, Ye.Yangibayeva, M.Akhmedov).

Textbooks and training manuals for the primary class (K. Kasimova, R.A. Mavlonova, L.Sh. Levenberg), manuals for teachers (MIMopo, A.M. Pishkalo, L.Sh .Levenberg, NUBikbayeva) and practice-test manuals for students (M.Ahmedov, M.Jumayev, N.Abdurakhmonova, R.Ibragimov, Yu.M.Kolyagin, PMYerdniyev) materials) they mentioned that it is possible to form the cognitive activity of primary school students.

In the works devoted to special issues of didactics and educational methodology (PMYerdniyev, NUBikbayeva, L.Sh. Levenberg, R.A. Mavlonova, K. Kasimova, etc.), this problem is considered in general, but it is separated as a special research subject. not received. Also, the issues of educational technology, independent work, and the use of game elements as a means of organizing problem solving in elementary grades have not been sufficiently studied.

Elementary school students are especially curious and diligent. Solving quick questions, tasks, riddles, logical problems and examples, rebuses, crosswords should become an interesting and constant activity for them.

Solving mathematical problems is an important component of teaching mathematics. It is impossible to imagine mastering mathematics without problems . The process of assimilation of theoretical materials studied in primary classes plays an important role in the development of students' thinking abilities.

Logical examples and problems are very important in the formation of ingenuity and ingenuity in students in mathematics classes. Logical examples and problems develop students' thinking and mental abilities. In them, quickness fulfills the tasks of expanding the scope of imagination and developing logical thinking. Examples of issues include:

Issue 1 . Place 12 checkers in four rows so that the number of checkers in each row is 4.

Issue 2 . It is necessary to distribute notebooks to several children. If each child is given 10 notebooks, 6 notebooks will be left over. If 11 are given, 5 notebooks will not be enough. Find the number of children?

Issue 3 . The number was reduced by 7, then the result was reduced 10 times, if the number was 34 less than the original number, find the original number?

Solving the above problems requires a lot of attention, quickness and resourcefulness from the students. Also, these issues are somewhat complicated. Students use arithmetic operations and calculations to solve these problems.

Pupils develop speed not only outside of class, but also during class. During the lesson, whether you work with students individually or as a group, if you work with them carefully with each problem or example, students will develop speed and activity. The following method is effective in developing speed and activity during the lesson. Students should not just work on the examples and problems in the textbook. In

particular, when problems arise, they can create new questions based on the conditions of the problem, not only finding its answer.

In the process of solving exercises, students get acquainted with facts that expand their imagination. With this, the scope of their differentiation expands and an organic connection is established between training and life (practice). Solving the exercises has a great impact on the mental development of students, and it forms the skills of analysis, comparison, generalization and abstract differentiation. The educational value of the exercises is also incomparable.

While performing the tasks listed above, at the same time, the exercises themselves become an object of direct learning, as well as a means of forming the necessary skills to solve them. Being able to solve the exercises involves a number of interrelated and integrally connected specific (separate) skills, which can be highlighted as follows;

1. Having read the exercise and understanding it, that is, being able to understand the meaning of each phrase and visualize the situation described in it;

2. Condition and question in the exercise. Be able to distinguish between known and unknown things;

3. To be able to determine the relationship between the condition and the question in the exercise, given and sought information, that is, to be able to analyze the text of the exercise and, as a result, to choose arithmetic operations to solve the exercise;

4. To be able to write the solution and answer to the exercise. These skills are formed in the course of regular and purposeful practice in the following stages:

1. Preparatory work.

2. Explanation of the text of the exercise.

3. Analyzing the exercise, looking for a way to solve it and drawing up a solution plan.

4. Write the solution and answer.

5. Working on the exercise after solving it.

At each stage of the training, the teacher uses different methods of solving the problem, taking into account the content of the problem, the level of preparation of the students, the didactic and educational nature of the training, and other factors.

The following can be included in the methodical methods for the formation of problem solving skills.

1. Face-to-face conversation with the student on the issue,
2. Explaining the issue using visual aids,
3. Comparison of issues;
4. Changing the matter, putting it into a different form;
5. Analyzing the text in the case of a lack or excess of a teaching in the conditions of the issues;
6. Compilation of problems by students;
7. Solving the problem in another way;
8. Check the solution of the problem;

It is better to use the phrase "Masala" at the stage of preparing to solve the problem. The purpose of the work in the preparatory period is to give children the opportunity to translate situations that occur in real life into the language of mathematical symbols. In this case, there is no need to create problems using pictures. It is better for children to write down the situation described in the form of a personal story in a notebook with mathematical symbols.

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